

Report on

IMPLEMENTATION OF ACCOUNTING FOR DECISION MAKING

INTRODUCTION:

On February 24, 2023 a lecture on "implementation of accounting for decision making" delivered by Dr. Jitendra Upadhyay. He is a committee chairman of accountancy in Tribhuvan University, he is also the research head of Nepal Commerce Campus.

OBJECTIVES:

The main objective of this classroom lecture is to make students aware about the use of accounting in everyday life as well as solve the queries students have about the particular topic of accounting. The lecture also aims to provide practical tips to consider for exam preparation as well as before, during and after the exam.

METHODOLOGY:

The lecture was conducted in a seminar format with a mix of stories, examples and interactive discussions. Mr. Upadhyay used real-life examples to illustrate the role of accounting information in decision making and provided practical tips and techniques for analyzing and interpreting financial statements. Participants were encouraged to ask questions and share their own experiences and insights regarding any subject's area i.e. share market, national economy and politics etc. One quote that really hit me is "a person who asks questions may look like a fool for 5 minutes but the person who does not ask questions because of fear and anxiety will be a fool for ever."

OUTCOMES:

The lecture has several positive outcomes for students. At first, he said that accounting is not only limited to debit-credit calculation, it is beyond that and used in small-scale industry and large-scale industry. He gave the examples of Rolls Royce, CG, Tesla etc. and how they make decisions based on accounting information they have. Secondly, he emphasized on things like how students need to prepare for an exam, how to be relaxed and remain calm during an exam and how much time should be taken to solve one question and what to do after finishing the exam. Thirdly, he described the typical users of accounting i.e. creditors, investors, lenders, customers, government, management etc.

SIGNIFICANCE:

The definition of accounting is not only limited to recording, interpreting, classifying, and analyzing of an organization's transactions in monetary terms, instead it is the art of taking the right decision at the right time using the existing information for the future.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the lecture on "implementation of accounting for decision making" delivered by Dr. Jitendra Upadhyay was a valuable experience that provided participants with practical insights to use in exam time as well as emerging users of accounting and the methods of accounting.

Some Clips of Programme

Energy Storage of Biomass

- Biomass is a renewable energy source that can be stored for long periods of time.
- Biomass can be stored in various forms, such as wood, crop residues, and animal manure.
- Biomass can be stored in a variety of ways, including open-air storage, silage, and pellets.
- Biomass storage is an important part of the biomass energy conversion process.

